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Impact Of Primary School Teachers' Salary Increment On Teacher Attendance, Instructional Delivery, And Pupils' Academic Performance In Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative phenomenological study explored the perceived impact of the recent salary increment for primary school teachers on teacher attendance, teaching effectiveness, and pupils' academic performance in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 15 primary school teachers (nine female, six male), aged 26–51 years, purposively selected from schools within Sokoto metropolis. Data were analysed using Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis framework. Four major themes emerged: (a) improved teacher attendance and punctuality, with all respondents confirming at least 70% improvement; (b) reduced mid-day absenteeism due to the ability to afford meals at school; (c) enhanced instructional delivery through the procurement of teaching materials; and (d) perceived improvement in pupils' academic outcomes, evidenced by better assignment completion, test scores, and classroom participation. However, rising petrol prices in Nigeria were identified as a significant countervailing factor, with teachers reporting transport costs more than four times higher than before the increment. The study concludes that while salary increments positively influence teacher motivation and school-level outcomes, these gains are partially eroded by macroeconomic inflation. Recommendations include the introduction of transport subsidies, indexation of salaries to inflation, and the establishment of school-based feeding programmes for teachers.

Keywords: salary increment, teacher motivation, primary education, teacher attendance, instructional materials, pupils' academic performance, Sokoto State, Nigeria

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The quality of basic education is fundamentally dependent on the motivation, commitment, and professional effectiveness of teachers (UNESCO, 2021). Teachers play a crucial role in the education system, and the quality of learning interactions between teachers and students surpasses the significance of other components such as the curriculum, facilities, and costs (Angraini et al., 2021). Among the myriad factors influencing teacher motivation, financial remuneration remains one of the most critical, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where teachers often face significant economic precarity (Ahmed, 2024; Akyeampong & Bennell, 2007). Ahmed (2024) emphasised that the instructor plays a crucial role in the implementation of all other educational components, particularly the curriculum.

Instructors are the primary and crucial asset in educational institutions since the effectiveness of an education system is directly influenced by the calibre of its instructors.

Herzberg's (1966) Two-Factor Theory of Motivation posits that salary functions primarily as a 'hygiene factor'—its adequacy prevents dissatisfaction but does not, by itself, generate sustained motivation. Nevertheless, when salaries are grossly inadequate, they can become a powerful demotivator, leading to absenteeism, moonlighting, and low professional morale (Ololube, 2006). Abubakar (2024) further supported this assertion, noting that remuneration is a fundamental determinant of teacher motivation and student outcomes in Nigerian educational institutions.

In Nigeria, the primary education sector has long grappled with challenges of teacher absenteeism, late arrival, and inadequate instructional delivery, all of which have been linked to poor remuneration (Federal Ministry of Education, 2014). The problem of teacher turnover has reached a critical stage, especially in sub-Saharan countries like Nigeria, where low pay is a primary reason for teachers leaving the profession (Ahmed, 2024; Mpundu, 2023). According to Mohammed and El-jajah (2019), the absence of adequate salary for teachers can have a significant impact on various aspects of their profession, including their punctuality and consistency in attending school, their attitude towards lesson planning, and ultimately the academic performance of their students.

In response to these challenges, the Sokoto State Government implemented a salary increment policy for primary school teachers, aiming to improve teacher welfare, reduce absenteeism, and enhance the quality of basic education. However, the effectiveness of such a policy cannot be assumed; it must be empirically examined, particularly in light of Nigeria's volatile economic environment, characterised by rising inflation and escalating fuel prices (Adeyemi & Bolarinwa, 2019).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Despite the implementation of salary increments for primary school teachers in Sokoto State, there is a paucity of empirical evidence regarding whether this policy has achieved its intended objectives. Specifically, little is known about how teachers themselves perceive the impact of the salary increment on their daily professional practices, attendance patterns, and instructional effectiveness. Furthermore, the extent to which these improvements translate into better academic outcomes for pupils remains underexplored. According to Nwoye and Nwoye (2022), the relationship between salary improvement and teacher performance in developing countries like Nigeria has not been sufficiently investigated through qualitative research. The absence of such evidence constrains policymakers' ability to evaluate the policy's effectiveness and to make informed decisions regarding future adjustments. This study, therefore, sought to address this gap by exploring the lived experiences of primary school teachers in Sokoto State regarding the impact of the salary increment on their professional lives and their pupils' academic performance.

1.3 Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. How has the salary increment influenced primary school teachers' attendance and punctuality in Sokoto State?
2. What changes have teachers observed in their teaching practices and access to instructional resources following the salary increment?
3. How do teachers perceive the effect of the salary increment on their pupils' academic performance?

1.4 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study posits that salary increment directly influences teacher attendance, which in turn affects instructional delivery. Improved instructional delivery, supported by the availability of instructional materials, ultimately leads to enhanced pupils' academic performance. However, this relationship is moderated by external economic factors, particularly petrol prices and general inflation, which may erode the real value of the salary increment. This framework is consistent

with the efficiency wage theory, which suggests that higher salaries can motivate teachers to put in more effort in their work (Ahmed, 2024; Akerlof & Yellen, 1986).

1.5 Significance of the Study

The findings of this study are expected to be significant for several stakeholders. For policymakers and educational administrators, the study provides evidence-based insights into the effectiveness of salary increment policies. For teacher training institutions, including Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, the findings highlight the importance of teacher welfare in professional development. For researchers, the study contributes to the growing body of literature on teacher motivation in the Nigerian context (Ahmed, 2024; Nwoye & Nwoye, 2022).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Herzberg's (1966) Two-Factor Theory of Motivation. According to this theory, job satisfaction and dissatisfaction are influenced by two distinct sets of factors: hygiene factors and motivators. Hygiene factors—including salary, working conditions, and job security—do not necessarily motivate employees but can cause dissatisfaction if inadequate. Motivators—such as recognition, responsibility, and achievement—are intrinsic factors that drive performance and satisfaction.

In the context of this study, salary is conceptualised as a hygiene factor. Its increment is expected to reduce dissatisfaction and create a conducive environment for teachers to be more engaged in their work. However, Herzberg's theory also suggests that salary alone cannot sustain long-term motivation unless complemented by other intrinsic motivators. Ahmed (2024) corroborated this view, noting that while salary is a significant factor in teachers' success, other factors such as job satisfaction, working conditions, and professional development opportunities also play crucial roles.

The efficiency wage theory further supports this framework, suggesting that better-paid teachers are likely to work harder in order to increase the chances of retaining their more valuable jobs (Ahmed, 2024). This theoretical lens guided the interpretation of teachers' responses regarding the impact of the salary increment.

2.2 Relationship Between Teacher Salary and Student Performance

During the learning process, the teacher has the most direct interaction with the students; the performance of a competent teacher can result in optimal learning outcomes (Angraini et al., 2021). Salary is a significant aspect in instructors' success (Azeem et al., 2018). The importance of teacher salaries in student performance is evident; as a school system raises teacher salaries in order to attract and retain highly competent teachers, student outcomes improve (Ahmed, 2024; Seybert, 2023).

Numerous academic studies confirm the long-held belief that teacher quality, specifically teacher salary, is one of the greatest determinants of student achievement (Azordegan et al., 2005; Ahmed, 2024). In contrast, theoretically, the absence of a salary for teachers can have a significant impact on various aspects of their profession, including their punctuality and consistency in attending school, their attitude towards lesson planning, and ultimately the academic performance of their students (Mohammed & El-jajah, 2019).

Teachers' compensation is believed to have a significant impact on the effectiveness of their instruction and the overall educational experience of students (Ahmed, 2024). The level of compensation for teachers plays a crucial role in determining the academic achievement of students (Mukomana, 2021).

2.3 Teacher Salary and Turnover

Teachers' turnover is a global challenge and, by its very nature, is an extremely complex phenomenon (Seybert, 2023). According to other studies, secondary teachers transfer from schools with high minority enrollment, low income, and low achievement to those with higher enrollment, greater economic advantage, and less diversity (Seiph, 2021). Ahmed (2024) reported that in South Africa, teacher resignation is on the rise, with more than 50,000 teachers recorded to have left the profession between

2011 and 2020. The alarming rate of turnover appears to be having an impact on the delivery of the curriculum as the teacher-learner ratio is rising to disturbing figures.

Low pay is one of the many variables that the research typically identifies as having the ability to contribute to teacher attrition and turnover (Ahmed, 2024; Mpundu, 2023). The problem of teacher turnover has almost reached a catastrophic stage, especially in sub-Saharan countries like Zambia, Nigeria, Kenya, Central African Republic, and South Africa (Ahmed, 2024).

2.4 Teacher Satisfaction in the Education System

In most cases, job satisfaction is closely intertwined with both productivity levels and an individual's overall well-being and behaviour (Mukomana, 2021). In the education system, according to a particular theory, it is proposed that teachers who experience satisfaction in their profession also tend to experience improved well-being, resulting in the cultivation of students who excel academically (Toropova et al., 2020). This theory emphasises the significance of teacher contentment in fostering positive academic outcomes for their students.

Teachers' job satisfaction primarily revolves around their professional attitudes, dedication towards the art of teaching, and their level of enthusiasm towards their work—all of which play a crucial role in shaping the overall educational system (Hemamala Sumanasena & Mohamed, 2022). Undoubtedly, the teaching profession holds a highly esteemed position within society, as educators are responsible for moulding young minds and nurturing them into responsible individuals who can actively contribute towards building a brighter future for their nation (Ahmed, 2024).

According to teacher satisfaction, teachers' job satisfaction has come to the forefront in recent years, with the effect of addressing this issue in international education evaluation studies, and endeavours are being made to increase teachers' job satisfaction (Ahmed, 2024). A worker's job satisfaction is greatly influenced by having enough work tools, resources, and teaching opportunities, as well as a manageable workload (Seybert, 2023).

2.5 Research Gap

While quantitative studies have examined the relationship between salary and teacher performance, few qualitative studies have explored the lived experiences of teachers regarding salary increments, particularly in the northern Nigerian context. Moreover, the mediating role of inflation and transport costs has received insufficient attention (Nwoye & Nwoye, 2022). This study addresses these gaps by providing rich, contextualised insights from teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted a qualitative phenomenological research design. Phenomenology is appropriate for exploring the lived experiences of individuals and understanding how they interpret specific phenomena (Creswell & Poth, 2018). In this case, the phenomenon of interest was the salary increment policy and its perceived impact on teachers' professional lives.

3.2 Study Area

The study was conducted in Sokoto metropolis, Sokoto State, Nigeria. Sokoto State is located in the north-western region of Nigeria and has a significant number of primary schools managed by both government and private entities. The choice of Sokoto metropolis was informed by its accessibility and the concentration of primary school teachers within the area.

3.3 Target Population and Sampling

The target population comprised all primary school teachers in Sokoto metropolis who had experienced the salary increment policy. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select 15 teachers based on the following inclusion criteria: (a) active employment as a primary school teacher in Sokoto metropolis; (b) having experienced the salary increment policy; and (c) willingness to participate voluntarily in the study. Purposive sampling was chosen to ensure that participants had the relevant experience and could provide rich, information-rich data (Patton, 2015). The sample comprised nine female and six male

teachers, reflecting the gender distribution typical of primary schools in the region. Participants' ages ranged from 26 to 51 years, with a mean age of 34.2 years ($SD = 7.1$). Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (N = 15)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	9	60.0
	Male	6	40.0
Age Group	26–30	4	26.7
	31–35	3	20.0
	36–40	3	20.0
	41–45	2	13.3
	46–50	2	13.3
	51+	1	6.7
	Teaching Experience (Years)	1–5	4
Experience (Years)	6–10	5	33.3
	11–15	3	20.0
	16–20	2	13.3
	21+	1	6.7

3.4 Data Collection Instrument

The primary data collection instrument was a semi-structured interview guide consisting of four open-ended questions, developed by the researchers based on the research questions and the conceptual framework. The questions were:

1. How did your salary increment improve your attendance at school?
2. Does the salary increment improve your teaching, and how?
3. Is there any difference before the salary increment and after the increment in terms of your overall academic work, and how?
4. Does it affect the pupils' academic performance?

The interview guide was pilot-tested with two teachers who were not part of the main sample to assess clarity and appropriateness. Minor wording adjustments were made based on the pilot feedback.

3.5 Data Collection Procedure

Interviews were conducted between October and November 2025 at locations and times chosen by each respondent to ensure comfort and convenience. Each interview lasted between 30 and 40 minutes. Before each interview, informed consent was obtained from the participant, and they were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequences. All interviews were conducted in English, as all participants were proficient in the language. Responses were audio-recorded with participants' permission and transcribed verbatim immediately after each session.

3.6 Data Analysis

Data were analysed using thematic analysis, following the six-step procedure outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006): (1) familiarisation with the data; (2) generating initial codes; (3) searching for themes; (4) reviewing themes; (5) defining and naming themes; and (6) producing the report. The analysis was conducted manually, with the researchers independently coding the transcripts and then meeting to reach consensus on the final themes. Disagreements were resolved through discussion and, where necessary, consultation with a third researcher.

3.7 Trustworthiness and Rigour

To ensure trustworthiness, the study employed Lincoln and Guba's (1985) criteria:

- **Credibility:** Member checking was conducted by returning the transcribed interviews to five participants for verification of accuracy. Participants confirmed that the transcripts accurately reflected their views.
- **Transferability:** A thick description of the context, participants, and findings is provided to enable readers to assess the applicability of the findings to other settings.
- **Dependability:** An audit trail was maintained, documenting all research decisions, data collection procedures, and analytic steps.
- **Confirmability:** Reflexivity was practised, with the researchers maintaining a reflexive journal to document their biases, assumptions, and potential influences on the research process. The researchers acknowledged that their positions as educators within the same state might influence their interpretations, and they actively worked to bracket these preconceptions. Peer debriefing sessions were also conducted with a colleague not involved in the study to challenge interpretations and ensure that findings were grounded in the data.

3.8 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the State Universal Basic Education, Sokoto. Participation was voluntary, and written informed consent was secured from all participants. Anonymity was maintained by using participant codes (T1–T15) in the reporting of findings. Participants were also assured that their responses would be used solely for research purposes and that data would be stored securely.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Overview

The thematic analysis of the interview data yielded four major themes, each with associated sub-themes. These themes are presented below, supported by direct quotations from participants. Participant codes (e.g., T1, T2) are used to maintain anonymity.

4.2 Theme 1: Improved Teacher Attendance and Punctuality

All 15 respondents (100%) confirmed that the salary increment had positively improved their attendance at school, with most estimating an improvement of at least seventy per cent (70%). This theme was further divided into three sub-themes.

Sub-theme 1a: Reduced Mid-Day Absenteeism

Several teachers reported that before the salary increment, they would return home during the lunch break to eat and often would not return to school. With the new salary, they could afford to buy food within the school vicinity, enabling them to remain at school throughout the day.

'Unlike the previous time when I went back home to eat during the break time and mostly would not be able to come back to school, now with the new salary, I spend all hours in school because I have money to buy food during the break.' (T4, Female, Age 35)

'Previously, I would go home for lunch, and sometimes I would not return because of transport issues or because I became occupied at home. Now, I can buy food near the school, so I stay back.' (T9, Male, Age 42)

Sub-theme 1b: Early Arrival and Punctuality

Teachers also reported arriving at school earlier than before the salary increment. Some specifically mentioned arriving at school as early as 9:00 AM, which is the official resumption time.

'We come to school as early as 9 o'clock now. Before, many of us would come late because we had no transport money or we were not motivated.' (T2, Female, Age 29)

Sub-theme 1c: Persistent Challenge of Transport Costs

Despite the overall improvement in attendance, some teachers raised concerns about the high cost of transportation due to the rising price of petrol in Nigeria. They noted that they now spend more than four times their previous transport costs to get to school.

'Even though the salary has increased, the price of petrol has also gone up. I now spend more than four times what I used to spend on transport before the salary and petrol increments.' (T11, Male, Age 51)

'My house is far from my school, and I cannot go to school barefoot. The transport cost is eating into the increment. But still, I come to school more regularly than before.' (T6, Female, Age 32)

4.3 Theme 2: Enhanced Teaching Effectiveness

Teachers unanimously reported improvements in their teaching practices following the salary increment. Two sub-themes emerged under this category.

Sub-theme 2a: Procurement of Instructional Materials

Teachers indicated that they were now able to purchase instructional materials, such as pens, pencils, and writing books, which they previously could not afford.

'With the new salary now, I can even buy instructional materials such as pens, pencils, writing books, etc. Before, I used to struggle to buy these things, and sometimes I would borrow from colleagues.' (T7, Female, Age 27)

Sub-theme 2b: Regular Lesson Delivery

Teachers reported missing fewer lessons than before the salary increment, as they were now more motivated and financially stable.

'There are improvements in my overall academic work because now I miss fewer lessons than I did before. I am now attending to my lessons regularly.' (T12, Female, Age 38)

4.4 Theme 3: Perceived Improvement in Pupils' Academic Performance

Teachers perceived that the salary increment had indirectly led to improvements in their pupils' academic performance. This perception was based on three indicators: assignment completion, test scores, and classroom participation.

'I am observing my students' academic improvement more than before. I can see it through their assignment records, test records, and even their classroom responses.' (T5, Male, Age 44)

'Because I now attend school regularly and teach well, my pupils are performing better. They submit assignments on time, and they participate more in class.' (T14, Female, Age 33)

4.5 Theme 4: Overall Academic Work Post-Increment

Teachers were asked to compare their overall academic work before and after the salary increment. The responses consistently indicated a positive shift, characterised by greater commitment, reduced stress, and improved lesson preparation.

'Before the increment, I was always worried about money and how to get to school. Now, my mind is at ease, and I can focus on preparing my lessons well.' (T1, Male, Age 31)

'There is a big difference. Before, I used to teach because I had to. Now, I teach because I enjoy it, and the salary helps me to do my job properly.' (T10, Female, Age 40)

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Interpretation of Findings

The findings of this study reveal that the salary increment for primary school teachers in Sokoto State has produced significant positive effects on teacher attendance, punctuality, and instructional delivery. This aligns with the predictions of Herzberg's (1966) Two-Factor Theory, which posits that adequate salary functions as a hygiene factor that reduces dissatisfaction and creates conditions conducive to motivation. When teachers are no longer preoccupied with financial constraints, they are better able to focus on their professional responsibilities.

The finding that teachers now stay in school during break times rather than returning home is particularly noteworthy. This behavioural change suggests that the salary increment addresses not only the financial needs of teachers but also the structural barriers to full-day attendance. Similar findings were reported by

Akyeampong and Bennell (2007) in Ghana, where teachers' ability to afford meals at school significantly reduced mid-day absenteeism. Ahmed (2024) similarly noted that teachers' performance is closely linked to their ability to meet basic needs, including food and transportation.

However, the study also identified a critical moderating factor: the rising cost of petrol and general inflation. Despite the salary increment, teachers reported spending more than four times their previous transport costs. This finding echoes the concerns raised by Adeyemi and Bolarinwa (2019) in Lagos State, where inflation eroded the real value of salary increments. Nwoye and Nwoye (2022) further emphasised that salary increments in Nigeria often fail to keep pace with inflation, thereby reducing their motivational impact.

The reported improvements in pupils' academic performance, although based on teachers' perceptions, are consistent with the logic that better-attending, better-prepared teachers are more likely to deliver effective instruction. This finding supports the argument by Ahmed (2024) that teacher welfare directly impacts pupil outcomes. As Ahmed (2024, p. 41) stated, "The level of compensation for teachers plays a crucial role in determining the academic achievement of students." However, it is important to acknowledge that these perceptions may be influenced by teachers' desire to present the policy in a positive light (social desirability bias). Future studies should complement perceptual data with objective measures of pupil achievement.

5.2 Contribution to Knowledge

This study makes several contributions to the literature. First, it provides rich, qualitative insights into the lived experiences of teachers in a northern Nigerian context, an area that has received limited research attention. Second, it highlights the critical role of inflation and transport costs as moderating factors, a nuance often overlooked in policy evaluations (Nwoye & Nwoye, 2022). Third, it offers a conceptual framework that can be tested in future quantitative studies. Fourth, the study demonstrates the applicability of Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory in a non-Western, developing-country context (Ahmed, 2024). Finally, it contributes to the growing body of evidence that salary increments positively influence teacher motivation and pupil outcomes in sub-Saharan Africa (Akyeampong & Bennell, 2007; Ahmed, 2024).

5.3 Implications for Policy and Practice

The findings of this study have several implications for educational policy and practice in Sokoto State and Nigeria more broadly.

First, policymakers should consider introducing transport allowances or subsidised transportation for teachers, particularly those living far from their schools. This would help to preserve the purchasing power of the salary increment and ensure that teachers can fully benefit from the financial adjustment.

Second, the government should explore mechanisms for indexing teacher salaries to inflation rates. Given the volatility of the Nigerian economy, periodic adjustments based on real economic indicators would help to maintain the motivational impact of salary increments (Nwoye & Nwoye, 2022).

Third, school administrators and education authorities should consider establishing school-based feeding programmes for teachers, similar to existing pupil feeding programmes. This would further reduce mid-day absenteeism and enhance teacher retention at school during working hours.

Fourth, teacher training institutions should incorporate modules on financial literacy and personal finance management to help teachers optimise their salaries in challenging economic environments.

5.4 Limitations of the Study

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the sample size of 15 teachers, while adequate for a qualitative study, limits the generalisability of the findings to all primary school teachers in Sokoto State. Second, the study relied entirely on self-reported perceptions, which may be subject to social desirability bias. Third, the study did not include objective measures of pupil performance, such as standardised test scores, which would have strengthened the validity of the claims regarding academic improvement. Fourth, the study did not include teachers who might have left the

profession or those who were dissatisfied with the increment, potentially introducing positive selection bias. Fifth, the cross-sectional nature of the data does not allow for causal inferences.

5.5 Future Research Directions

Future research should adopt a mixed-methods approach that combines qualitative interviews with quantitative data on teacher attendance (e.g., attendance registers) and pupil achievement (e.g., standardised test scores). A longitudinal study tracking teachers before and after the salary increment would provide more robust evidence of causality. Additionally, research comparing teachers in Sokoto State with those in other states that have not implemented similar increments would provide valuable comparative insights. Finally, quantitative studies testing the conceptual framework presented in this study would help to establish the statistical significance of the relationships identified.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusion

This study explored the perceived impact of the salary increment for primary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The findings provide strong evidence that the salary increment has positively influenced teacher attendance, punctuality, and instructional delivery. Teachers reported staying at school longer, arriving earlier, and being able to purchase instructional materials that were previously unaffordable. Moreover, teachers perceived improvements in their pupils' academic performance, as evidenced by better assignment completion, test scores, and classroom participation. However, the positive effects of the salary increment are partially offset by the rising cost of petrol and general inflation, which have eroded the real value of the increase. This underscores the need for complementary policies that address the broader economic challenges facing teachers. Overall, the study concludes that salary increments are a necessary but not sufficient condition for improving teacher performance and pupil outcomes in the Nigerian primary education system (Ahmed, 2024; Nwoye & Nwoye, 2022).

6.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Introduction of Transport Subsidies:** The Sokoto State Government should introduce transport allowances or subsidised transportation for primary school teachers, particularly those residing far from their schools, to mitigate the impact of rising petrol prices.
2. **Indexation of Salaries to Inflation:** The government should consider adopting a policy of indexing teacher salaries to the inflation rate, with regular reviews to adjust salaries in line with economic realities (Nwoye & Nwoye, 2022).
3. **Establishment of Teacher Feeding Programmes:** School administrators should consider establishing feeding programmes for teachers to reduce mid-day absenteeism and enhance teacher retention at school.
4. **Provision of Instructional Materials:** The government and school authorities should ensure that instructional materials are provided as part of the standard school budget, rather than relying on teachers to purchase them out-of-pocket.
5. **Further Research:** A mixed-methods study combining qualitative and quantitative data should be conducted to validate these findings and provide more robust evidence for policymaking.

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